

THE INNOVATIVE METHODS FOR PRE-WRITING.**Janiqulov Jaloliddin Orifjon o'g'li***Navoi State Pedagogical institute,**English language and literature faculty student*Scientific adviser **Istamova Dilnoza Sadullayevna**

Annotation: This article gives information about how improve our writing skills in teaching writing and also tell one of the most important things to remember when teaching writing is that writing is a process.

Key words: writing, brainstorming, free writing, journalist questionnaire, cluster mapping

Very few native speakers will ever start writing at the top of the first page and continue straight through until they finish at bottom of the last one. The entire process has five steps, but the first step in the writing process is coming up with your thoughts and ideas, also known as prewriting. Prewriting helps students gather ideas and give them a bank of possibilities for their writing. This way, as students write they do not have to make decisions simultaneously about content and language. Help your students get a head start before they write with any of these methods for prewriting. The bank of ideas they will generate will be an invaluable resource as they write.

Brainstorming is an activity with which most people are familiar. The object in brainstorming is to compile as large a list as possible of potential examples for a given topic. This is a great activity to do in small groups or with the entire class. Brainstorming a list of ice cream flavors is an easy one to start with when introducing the concept. Naturally, one idea will spark another, so it is helpful to have students working together when brainstorming. Give your students permission to be as creative as they like. Anything goes with brainstorming. Challenge your

students to come up with as many examples as they possibly can for whatever topic you give them.

Free writing is an individual activity for getting thoughts from your head on to paper. Explain the concept of stream of consciousness to your students and tell them that free writing is simply putting on paper every thought that is going through their heads. Like with brainstorming, anything goes. The goal of this activity is to never let your pen or pencil stop writing. Help students understand that though they will begin with a particular topic in mind, it is okay to veer off on tangents as they write. Spelling and grammar are not important for this activity; it is ideas that we are trying to grasp. Give your students a set length of time for this activity. If they are young you may want to limit it to two or three minutes; older students can probably write for five to ten minutes. Then when students have completed the activity, have them go back and read what they have written digging through the mire for the gems hidden within.

Journalistic questions approach a topic in a more structured manner. Start by reviewing the question words: who, what, where, when, why and how. Then, for your given topic, ask questions starting with each of these words. For example, if your topic was study habits, you might ask, “Who has good study habits? Who benefits from good study habits? What are the good habits? Where do people with good study habits study? Where do they keep their books? Where do they organize notes and homework? When do they study? When do they complete assignments? ...” There are an infinite number of questions you can ask about any given subject. This activity can be done either individually or in groups with success. Have students write answers to each question. When finished prewriting, have them go back and read what they have written and organize their thoughts in preparation for writing. Cluster mapping, also called idea webbing, is a great way to show relationships between ideas. Cluster mapping is also part idea generation and part organization, so students will know exactly how to group their ideas once they are ready to write. To begin, write your topic in the center of the page and put a circle around it. Then

you can move in one of two directions. With younger children, have them think of questions about the topic. For example, if the topic is spiders, they may ask, “What do spiders eat? Where do spiders live? What do spiders look like?” Each question should be written in a bubble connected to the central topic. Tell students to spread these bubbles out over the page as they will be adding to each. Then, have students answer the questions connecting still smaller bubbles to the bubbles containing the questions. If their question was “What do spiders do?” then they might make connecting bubbles saying they capture flies, they spin webs, they scare nursery rhyme characters, etc. With students who have more knowledge about their central topic, their bubbles connected to the central idea should include subtopics and/or details about the subtopics. A student may start with spiders as the central theme, make a connecting bubble with the subtopic of diet, then connect bubbles to that subtopic with different types of insects on which spiders feed. Generally speaking, each of the subtopics would be one paragraph in a composed piece of writing with examples and support for the idea surrounding it.

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